

Preprint citation patterns since the COVID-19 pandemic

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Challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as recent science policy initiatives, induced increasing interest in preprints as a format for scholarly communication. However, regarding their use and acceptance by scholars, preprints still seem in an uncertain position. We aim to shed light on the actors who cite preprints by analyzing (1) which publishers' publications make particularly high use of preprints and (2) whether authors who have themselves posted preprints (or published other forms of Open Access) are also more likely to cite preprints (or other forms of Open Access). Our findings indicate some substantial differences between citation patterns of a set of COVID-19-related preprints and a similar control set of non-preprints, as well as a correlation between authors' Open-Access-affinity when publishing and their Open-Access-affinity when citing. Our future work will go into better differentiation between disciplines and research fields.

1. Introduction

With the development of the Internet and the need to increase the speed of the publication process of scholarly literature, new types of scholarly research publications have arisen, such as preprints, datasets, or open lab books, e.g., Jupyter Notebooks. For some of those new research outputs the publication industry as well as the scholarly community were quick to propose various kinds of tools, metrics, and indicators, to track and reflect their usage in scholarly communication, such as Clarivate's Data Citation Index, the DataCite Initiative, or other metrics for data (Champieux, & Coates, 2022). Such rather formal ways of recognition 'ennoble' those research outputs and incentivize their publication as well as reuse within the scholarly community - and lack of them hinders adoption (Alperin et al., 2022; Pierce et al., 2019). Although Open Access (OA) publishing has experienced a strong push from science policy, especially with regard to the open science movement and the recent COVID-19 pandemic, particularly preprints - a form of green OA publishing - are still awaiting similar ennoblement. They do not count as formal publications because they have not undergone peer review and therefore do not count as citable items in Web of Science (McVeigh & Mann, 2009), amongst others - which is the case for most published datasets, too, but which does not seem to pose barriers against their use (Gregory et al., 2023). Anyway, the scholarly community is often cautioned against (Teixeira da Silva, 2017; 2021) or, in general, reluctant to cite preprints directly (Chiarelli et al., 2019). However, this reluctance seemed to have decreased during the pandemic: An analysis of preprints on bioRxiv has shown that preprints are cited, regardless of whether they lead to a journal article at a later date (Fraser et al., 2020).

This is the motivation for our study: to learn more about the actors citing preprints. We aim to shed light on the citation image of preprints (modified after Cronin & Shaw, 2002), especially with regard to publications on COVID-19, and the preprint citation practices of authors posting preprints. Two research questions guide our work:

- 1) Which sources (on publisher level) cite COVID-19-related bioRxiv- and medRxiv-preprints and how does this citation image differ from the citation image of a comparable random set of non-preprint-publications?
- 2) To what extent do authors who post preprints (and other forms of OA literature) themselves expose a higher tendency to also cite preprints (and other forms of OA literature) in their works?

2. Related work

Unlike in economics or physics, where there is a strong preprint culture, the posting of preprints is a relatively new phenomenon in the life sciences (Chiarelli et al., 2019; Puebla et al., 2022; Xie et al., 2021). The rising importance and spread of preprints in the life sciences as indicated by increased citations and altmetric indicators is particularly evident at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic (Fraser et al., 2021). Among corresponding authors of COVID-19 preprints, 85% posted a preprint for their first time during the pandemic (compared to 69% of corresponding authors of non-COVID-19 preprints). At 58%, the proportion of COVID-19 preprints that were cited at least once was significantly higher than that of non-COVID-19 preprints (22%) (Fraser et al., 2021).

Journal articles that were previously posted as a preprint are cited more often and receive more attention online (Añazco et al., 2021; Fraser et al., 2020). According to the analysis of preprints on bioRxiv, preprint-based journal articles have a citation advantage of 63.1% compared to articles that were published in the same journal and in the same month but are not based on a preprint (Fraser et al., 2020). Despite the empirical evidence highlighting the benefits of posting preprints during the COVID-19 pandemic, researchers in the life sciences were more cautious about expectations of benefits (Biesenbender et al., 2024; Fraser et al., 2022), which is not the case to the same extent for other disciplines such as economics, social sciences, or oceanography (Biesenbender, Smirnova et al., 2024).

3. Method & Data

To analyze which publishers cite COVID-19-related preprints, our starting point are the DOIs of all COVID-19-related preprints posted on bioRxiv and medRxiv between 2020 and 2022, which we retrieve from the Dimensions API. To distinguish COVID-19-related preprints, we use the following search string introduced by Fraser & Kramer (2020) across titles and abstracts: “coronavirus | covid-19 | sars-cov | ncov-2019 | 2019-ncov | sars-2”. This leads to 26,906 unique DOIs belonging to COVID-19-related preprints. To fetch additional metadata we match these DOIs with OpenAlex, which reduces our dataset to 26,899 preprints, as for 7 DOIs no OpenAlex record can be found. We also use OpenAlex to retrieve all instances of these preprints being cited (n=196,039) as well as the metadata of the citing documents’ (n=89,732). All OpenAlex data collected in this study reflects a state from January 2024.

For comparison purposes, we also construct a control set consisting of COVID-19-related non-preprint research articles published within the same time frames as our preprints. To do this, we start with Dimensions’ COVID-19 publication dataset published via Google Big Query¹, from which we extract the DOIs of all non-preprint publications published between 2020 and 2022. We match these with OpenAlex, restricting the set to documents of type ‘article’. From this pool, we randomly select one control article for each preprint in our preprint set that was published within the same year and month. This procedure leaves us with a control set of the same size as our preprint set (n=26,899). Again, we retrieve instances of

¹ <https://console.cloud.google.com/marketplace/product/digital-science-public/covid-19-dataset-dimensions>

these non-preprints being cited (n=634,512) as well as the citing documents' (n=351,798) metadata from OpenAlex. To answer our first research question, we then analyze the shares of individual publishers among the documents citing our set of COVID-19-related preprints and compare these to the publishers among the documents citing our control set of COVID-19-related non-preprint articles.

For our second research question - whether authors who regularly post preprints or publish other forms of OA literature also tend to cite larger shares of OA literature - we start with a random sample of 100,000 authors selected from all authors who since January 2020 first-authored at least one publication according to OpenAlex. We exclude any authors who in the 48 months of observation (January 2020 to December 2023) published more than 48 articles as first authors, as such high numbers of publications per individual likely resulted from disambiguation errors within the OpenAlex database.

For the sample of 100,000 authors created this way, we obtain all first-authored publications of type 'article' published since January 2020, as well as those articles' OA status, as a basis to assess the authors' recent OA publication behaviors. We assign each author to one of five classes, according to the share of OA among their publications over the past four years, as explained in Table 1. Differently from green, gold, or hybrid OA, we here group bronze OA together with closed access, as bronze OA publications usually would originally have been closed access publications for which the publishing journal temporarily grants open accessibility - thus, bronze OA publications cannot be considered expressions of the respective authors' choices to publish their findings in OA.

To investigate potential correlations between authors' OA affinity in their publishing and in their citing behavior, we as a last step gather the metadata of all documents that were cited within our author sample's first-authored publications since 2020 from OpenAlex, along with those cited documents' OA status.

Table 1. Classes of individual authors' Open Access publication behavior.

Class	Description
OA only	100% of publications* were either of type green, gold, or hybrid Open Access.
Majority OA	More than 50% but less than 100% of publications* were either of type green, gold, or hybrid Open Access.
Equal	Exactly 50% of publications* were either of type green, gold, or hybrid Open Access.
Majority Closed	More than 50% but less than 100% of publications* were either of type bronze Open Access or closed access.
Closed only	100% of publications* were either of type bronze Open Access or closed access.

*refers to share of respective author's first-authored publications between January 2020 and December 2023

4. Intermediate Results and Discussion

4.1. RQ1: From which publishers do the documents citing preprints come from?

Figure 1 shows the shares of individual publishers among the documents citing our two sets. We see for instance that publications by *Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory* (CSHL; the institute maintaining both bioRxiv and medRxiv) are responsible for the largest share of citations of our preprints (22.6%), while *Elsevier* publications are the most numerous among documents citing our set of non-preprints (17.9%).

Figure 1: Relative publisher frequencies among citations of the two sets.

To account for the fact that publishers with higher publication output will naturally have higher shares of citations among both groups, Figure 2 shows annual citations per publisher, normalized by the total number of publications that publisher had according to OpenAlex that year. The result is a score that can be interpreted as the average number of citations to our respective sample contained in a publication from that publisher in the given year. To focus our attention on the more prominent medium to high output publishers, those with less than 1,000 publications in a given year were excluded from this part of the analysis.

The high shares of the preprint publisher CSHL (as well as *F1000*) reflect the significant role that preprints fulfilled within the COVID-19-related scholarly exchange as a quick communication tool, especially early years of the pandemic: preprints were both most frequently cited by other preprints (indicated in Figure 1), as well as themselves making use of other preprints particularly often (indicated in Figure 2). Over the years, the likelihood of a CSHL-preprint citing another preprint went down substantially, which might reflect how COVID-19 preprints were as sources of knowledge over time superseded by formal publications on the matter, even for preprint authors.

Figure 2: Normalized annual publisher frequencies among citations of the two sets.

4.2. RQ2: Do authors who post preprints expose a higher tendency to also cite OA?

Figure 3a shows the shares of authors within our random sample as categorized based on their recent OA publication behaviour (n=100,000). Most authors belong either to the class “Closed only”, followed by “OA only” (a relative advantage of these classes compared to the three in between was to be expected, as authors with only one first-authored publication since 2020 could naturally only be categorized into one of the Only-classes). Figure 3b shows the classes’ shares if we exclude all authors with only one qualifying publication (which reduces the sample to n=40,210). In both cases, we see about equal shares of authors in the classes “Majority Closed” and “Majority OA”.

Figures 3a & 3b: Shares of classes of individual authors' recent publication behavior.

In Figure 4, we see the shares that publications of different OA status types make up among the citations in publications of authors from our five classes. It seems noteworthy that the less OA-affine authors also cite larger proportions of closed access literature, while the shares of citations for all other OA status types increase along with the authors' OA-affinity. Specifically regarding the shares of cited preprints (i.e., OA status *green*), Kruskal-Wallis one-way ANOVA followed by post-hoc pairwise Wilcoxon tests confirm the statistical significance of differences between all groups with $p < .001$ (Bonferroni-adjusted).

Figure 4: Shares of OA status types among documents cited by authors from the five publication behavior classes.

5. Conclusions and Outlook

Adding to findings by Fraser et al. (2021) on the use of preprints during the pandemic, our results concerning our first research question indicate the high intensity with which the preprint-authoring community interacted among itself by referencing other preprints within preprints, especially in the pandemic's early stages. Moreover, they show that formal publications from conventional publishers (e.g., Nature, Springer) also made substantial use

of COVID-19 preprints and cited them accordingly, although in several cases to a considerably lesser extent than they cited publications from our non-preprint control set (e.g., Elsevier, Wiley-Blackwell, Taylor & Francis). It remains to be investigated whether this apparent varying preprint-affinity between publishers can be explained by publishers' citation policies, or by their varying emphases on preprint-affine fields of research. As another part of future work, we will qualitatively analyze the preprints that were used particularly frequently to see whether certain types of preprints attract particularly frequent use within preprint- or non-preprint literature.

The results concerning our second research question suggest a correlation between authors' willingness to publish OA and their inclination to cite literature of various OA types in their works. Again, further research remains necessary to determine the explaining mechanisms: in particular, we prospectively aim to investigate to which degree this correlation can be explained by overall discipline-specific peculiarities regarding openness towards OA, as well as how self-citations affect our analysis.

Our work comes with limitations. First, in our author-level analysis we rely on the disambiguation provided by OpenAlex. Across our study we encountered a few authors with thousands of first-authored publications in the database - which might indicate existing limitations said disambiguation has yet to solve. Furthermore, the choice of database can have significant effects on the amount of retrievable citations (see also Wang et al., 2020 for the case of preprints specifically). Thus, reproducing our analysis on further databases (i.e., Web of Science, Scopus) could help to validate our findings. Lastly, so far we did not differentiate between disciplines - which, as highlighted above, appears to be the natural next step to arrive at more precise and informative conclusions about the relationship between OA publishing and citing behavior.

Open science practices

The programming scripts used in this study's analyses are openly available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12634717>).

Acknowledgments

OpenAlex data was obtained via participation in the *Kompetenznetzwerk Bibliometrie* (16WIK2101A), funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research.

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Competing interests

The ZBW Leibniz Information Center for Economics is host of EconStor (<https://www.econstor.eu>), a publication server for scholarly economic literature, provided as a non-commercial public service. The authors declare no further conflicts of interest.

Funding information

This work was funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) project Open Access Effects – The Influence of Structural and Author-specific Factors on the Impact of OA (OASE), grant number 16PU17005A/16PU17005B.

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